

Knowledge and Practice of Cardio-Pulmonary Resuscitation among Health Workers in Catholic Hospital Oluyoro and Jericho Specialist Hospital, Ibadan, Oyo State

AUTHOR(S): KADRI Adenike Koseganlola R. , SALAKO, Esther Omobolanle, OTUFALE, Taiwo Adenike, OLAOYE, Elizbeth Bolanle

Abstract

Cardiac arrest is a major global public health concern, accounting for approximately 15–20% of all deaths worldwide and contributing to significant cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. Cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) remains the cornerstone of emergency care for victims of cardiac arrest and related emergencies, as it maintains circulation to vital organs until advanced interventions are available. Despite its importance, gaps in CPR knowledge and practice persist, particularly in developing countries such as Nigeria, where nationwide training programmes are limited. This study assessed the knowledge and practice of CPR among health workers in Catholic Hospital Oluyoro and Jericho Specialist Hospital, Ibadan. A descriptive cross-sectional design was employed with 126 respondents recruited through multistage sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analysed with SPSS version 25. Findings revealed that most respondents demonstrated strong knowledge of CPR fundamentals, including compression-ventilation ratios, chest compression techniques, and patient positioning. However, notable gaps were identified in advanced interventions such as defibrillation use, paediatric resuscitation techniques, and accurate compression depths for infants. Furthermore, although two-thirds of participants reported good practice, inconsistencies remained in applying correct procedures under varying circumstances. The chi-square analysis indicated no statistically significant relationship between knowledge and practice ($p = 0.086$), suggesting that factors such as confidence, frequency of retraining, and hands-on exposure may influence competence. The study concludes that while health workers possess substantial CPR knowledge, periodic, structured, and simulation-based training is essential to enhance practical application, reduce mortality, and improve outcomes in cardiac emergencies.

E.G.C.S.J

Accepted 15 December 2025
Published 22 December 2025
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18024358

Keywords: Cardiac arrest, Cardiopulmonary resuscitation, Health workers, Knowledge, Practice, Emergency care,

**ABOUT
AUTHOR**

Author(s):

KADRI Adenike Koseganlola R.

Department of Nursing,
Lead City University, Ibadan

SALAKO, Esther Omobolanle

Department of Nursing,
Lead City University, Ibadan

OTUFALE, Taiwo Adenike

Department of Nursing,
Lead City University, Ibadan

OLAOYE, Elizbeth Bolanle

Department of Nursing,
Lead City University, Ibadan

Introduction

Cardiac arrest remains a major global public health concern, demanding attention from both medical professionals and the general population. The challenge is especially significant in developing countries where knowledge of cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) is often insufficient, and even those with some understanding may lack the practical skills required to perform it effectively. The ability to intervene promptly during emergencies such as cardiac arrest, suffocation, drowning, or burn-related incidents is critical in reducing morbidity and mortality rates. Nurses are often the first to recognise the need for CPR in hospital settings, highlighting the necessity for all health professionals—and indeed the wider public—to possess basic CPR knowledge. Without this widespread competence, preventable deaths may continue to occur in hospitals and communities. Onyeka et al. (2022) emphasised that the successful delivery of CPR by trained healthcare professionals plays a significant role in reducing in-hospital fatalities, thus underscoring the urgency of widespread CPR education. The scale of the problem is highlighted by global data, which shows that cardiac arrest is estimated to account for 15–20% of all deaths and is a leading cause of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality in both developed and developing contexts. Previous research has revealed that more than three million sudden cardiac deaths occur annually worldwide, with survival rates alarmingly below 8% (Olajumoke, et al., 2019). CPR, an integral part of emergency medical care, combines chest compressions with artificial ventilation to maintain circulation to the brain and vital organs until more advanced treatment becomes available (Oluwasanmi et al., 2025). This intervention has been consistently recognised as one of the most effective life-saving techniques in cardiac arrest situations. Its success, however, depends on the timely and competent response of healthcare professionals, making the promotion of CPR training a priority for reducing fatalities in hospital and community settings (Cortegiani et al., 2019)

Despite its significance, inadequate knowledge and poor confidence in performing CPR have been reported among healthcare trainees across various regions (Adewale et al., 2020). Studies in Europe have revealed low confidence levels among medical students in initiating CPR, while similar deficiencies in knowledge have been observed in Switzerland and Pakistan (Alsharari et al., 2018; Grasner et al., 2016). Training approaches have also evolved, with the American Heart Association (AHA, 2010) shifting from the traditional ABC (Airway, Breathing, Circulation) sequence to CAB (Chest compression, Airway, Breathing), reflecting the growing importance of early chest compressions (Saidu et al., 2023). However, evidence suggests that poor training persists, with undergraduates in nursing and allied professions in countries such as the UK and Poland also demonstrating gaps in CPR competence. This highlights the pressing need for both basic and advanced life support training across all health disciplines, given that professionals frequently encounter emergency cases in clinical practice.

In many developing countries, including Nigeria, the challenge is exacerbated by the absence of standardised nationwide CPR training programmes for healthcare workers, irrespective of their area of practice. This has resulted in significant gaps in both knowledge and practical skills among nurses and other frontline workers (Gbenga-Epebinu et al., 2022). The lack of structured training frameworks not only undermines the capacity of healthcare professionals to respond to emergencies but also contributes to avoidable deaths and poor health outcomes. Addressing these gaps requires deliberate policy action, institutional reforms, and

stronger emphasis on simulation-based and hands-on training for both students and practicing professionals (Oluwasanmi et al., 2025; Olofin-Samuel et al., 2024).

Given these realities, there is a clear and urgent need to establish ongoing, periodic, and repeated CPR training programmes that combine both theoretical and practical components. Such initiatives would not only improve the competence of health professionals but also contribute to reducing mortality rates and minimising neurological disabilities associated with cardiac arrest. Continuous education and practice ensure that health workers retain the confidence and skill required to act effectively during emergencies. It is against this backdrop that the present study seeks to assess the knowledge of cardiopulmonary resuscitation among health workers in Catholic Hospital Oluyoro and Jericho Specialist Hospital, located in the Ibadan South-East Local Government Area. Findings from this study will provide insights into the current state of CPR knowledge, identify critical gaps, and inform recommendations for strengthening medical education and professional practice in Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design, specifically a quantitative cross-sectional approach, to assess the knowledge and practice of cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) among health workers. The target population comprised health workers working in selected hospitals within Ibadan South-East and Ibadan South-West Local Government Areas of Oyo State. A total of 126 respondents were recruited through a multistage sampling technique, ensuring representation across different professional categories. The design was considered suitable as it enabled the collection of standardised information within a defined period, providing an accurate picture of the knowledge and practice levels of CPR among the respondents.

Data were collected using a self-developed structured questionnaire designed to capture respondents' knowledge and practice of CPR. All items in the instrument were closed-ended to allow for easy categorisation and analysis. The completed questionnaires were coded, and data were entered into EpiData version 3.1 before being exported to the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 for analysis. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed, with two research questions and one hypothesis raised and tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The use of SPSS facilitated rigorous statistical analysis, ensuring accuracy and reliability in interpreting the results of the study.

Results

Table 1 Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency (n=126)	Percent (%)
Age (in years)	20-29	42	33
	30-39	53	42.1
	40-49	24	19.0
	50-59	7	5.6
	Total	126	100.0
Gender	Male	59	46.8

	Female	67	53.2
	Total	126	100.0
Marital status	Single	40	31.7
	Married	78	61.9
	Widowed	3	2.4
	Divorced/Separated	5	4.0
	Total	126	100.0
Religion	Christianity	71	56.3
	Islam	49	38.9
	Traditional	6	4.8
	Total	126	100.0
Professional	Nurse	54	42.9
	Medical Doctor	33	26.2
	Emergency Technicians	12	9.5
	Midwives	11	8.7
	Pharmacists	4	3.2
	Medical Laboratory	12	9.5
	Total	126	100.0
Educational Status	HND	14	11.1
	BSc/BNSc	69	54.8
	DDM	533	4.0
	MBBS	33	14.3
	MSc	5	4.0

	Total	126	100.0
Ethnicity	Yoruba	91	72.2
	Igbo	27	21.4
	Hausa	4	3.2
	Others	4	3.2
	Total	126	100.0
Year of Experience	<5	52	41.3
	6-10	62	49.5
	11-15	9	7.0
	16-20	1	0.8
	>20	2	1.6
	Total	126	100.0

The socio-demographic characteristics of respondents reveal that the study participants were fairly diverse but with some notable concentrations in specific groups. In terms of age, the largest proportion of respondents (42.1%) fell within the 30–39 years category, followed by 33.0% in the 20–29 years range, indicating that the respondents were predominantly young to middle-aged adults. Gender distribution showed a slight female majority (53.2%) compared to males (46.8%). Marital status highlighted that most respondents were married (61.9%), while 31.7% were single, and only a few were widowed (2.4%) or divorced/separated (4.0%). Religious affiliation was largely dominated by Christianity (56.3%), with Islam accounting for 38.9% and traditional religion making up just 4.8%. This reflects the religious demographics commonly observed in Southwestern Nigeria.

With respect to profession, nurses constituted the largest group (42.9%), followed by medical doctors (26.2%), while emergency technicians, midwives, medical laboratory scientists, and pharmacists accounted for smaller proportions. Educational status showed that more than half of the respondents (54.8%) held a BSc/BNSc degree, while 14.3% had MBBS qualifications, and a smaller proportion had postgraduate degrees such as MSc (4.0%). Ethnic distribution revealed a predominance of Yoruba respondents (72.2%), with Igbo making up 21.4% and Hausa and others constituting a minority (3.2% each). Regarding years of experience, nearly half (49.5%) had 6–10 years of professional experience, while 41.3% had less than five years, and only a small number (7.8%) had more than 10 years. This indicates that the respondents were mostly early to mid-career professionals, suggesting a workforce with considerable energy and exposure but still developing in long-term experience.

Table 2: Knowledge of Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation among Respondents

Variables	Responses (n=126)		
	Yes f(%)	No f(%)	I don't Know
CPR stand for Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation	125(99.2)	1(0.8)	0(0)
CPR support and maintain breathing and circulation	125(99.2)	1(0.8)	0(0)
Hand placement for Chest Compression during CPR should be at the lower half of breastbone	124(98.4)	2(1.6)	0(0)

Nose pinch is the preferred method for opening the Airway during CPR	18(14.3)	106(84.1)	2(1.6)
Defibrillator should be used for ventricular fibrillation and pulseless ventricular tachycardia	68(54.0)	58(46.0)	0(0)
Compression ventilation ratio is 30:2	119(94.4)	7(5.6)	0(0)
The rate of compression is 100-120 per minute	98(77.8)	22(22.2)	0(0)
CPR for infants is done using two fingers	121(94.5)	7(5.5)	0(0)
Interruption of compression should occur during pulse check	113(88.1)	15(11.9)	0(0)
Interruption of compression should occur during defibrillation	23(18.3)	103(81.7)	0(0)
CPR should be done on every person in cardiac emergency	119(94.4)	7(5.6)	0(0)
Depth of chest compression during CPR for infant is appropriately 1 inch (2.5 cm)	7(5.6)	119(94.4)	0(0)
Depth of chest compression during CPR for infant is appropriately 1.5 inch (4 cm)	126(100.0)	0(0)	0(0)
Chest compression during CPR stimulates 25% heart functioning	125(99.2)	1(0.8)	0(0)

The results in Table 2 indicate that respondents demonstrated a generally high level of knowledge regarding core aspects of Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation (CPR). Almost all participants correctly recognized that CPR stands for Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation, that it supports breathing and circulation, and that chest compressions should be placed at the lower half of the breastbone. Similarly, the majority showed strong knowledge of compression-ventilation ratio, compression rate, and the correct use of two fingers for infants. The high proportion of correct responses in these areas reflects a solid foundational understanding of CPR principles and their application in emergency situations. This suggests that the respondents are well-informed about the essential steps required to sustain life during cardiac arrest, particularly with regard to adult CPR procedures.

However, the findings also highlight notable gaps in specific areas of CPR knowledge. Most respondents were unaware that nose pinching is not the preferred method of opening the airway during CPR, and many lacked clarity about the correct interruptions during defibrillation. There was also confusion regarding the depth of chest compression for infants, with a large majority incorrectly identifying 1 inch instead of 1.5 inches. Furthermore, almost half of the respondents did not know that a defibrillator should be used for ventricular fibrillation and pulseless ventricular tachycardia. These gaps suggest that while general awareness of CPR exists, there are critical misconceptions regarding paediatric application, airway management, and advanced interventions such as defibrillation. Addressing these knowledge gaps through targeted training and refresher courses could enhance respondents' competence and ensure more accurate application of CPR techniques in real-life emergencies.

Table 3 Practice of Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation

Variable	Categories	Frequency(n=126)	Percent (%)
Performed CPR on patient in cardiac emergency	Yes	126	100.0
	No	0	0
	Total	126	100.0

If yes, how many times	1-3	70	56.6
	4 -7	54	42.9
	>7	2	1.6
	Total	122	100.0
	Mean±SD		3.96± 2.467
Checks for patient pulse rate before commencing CPR	Yes	126	100.0
	No	0	0
	Total	126	100.0
Ensures person in cardiac emergency is laid supine on a relatively hard surface before commencing CPR	Yes	121	96.0
	No	5	4.0
	Total	126	100.0
Uses the same procedure to administer both children and adults	Yes	30	23.8
	No	96	76.21
	Total	126	100.0
Chest compression rate practiced	150 per min	7	5.6
	100 per min	105	83.3
	50 per min	9	7.1
	I don't know	5	4.0
	Total	126	100.0
Rate compression: mouth -to- mouth ventilation utilized	15:2	10	7.9
	30:2	116	92.1
	Total	126	100.0
Rate compression: mouth-to-mouth	15:2	116	92.1
Location of chest compression	Upper part of the chest	0	0
	Middle part of the chest	41	32.5
	Lower part of the chest	85	67.5
	Total	126	100.0
Depth of compression	At least 1-2 cm	46	36.5
	Moderate, 5-6 cm	78	61.9
	As much as possible	2	1.6
	Total	126	100.0

The findings in Table 3 demonstrate that all respondents reported having performed cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) in cardiac emergencies, with most having done so between one and seven times. This suggests that the respondents were not only trained but had practical exposure to real-life emergency situations. Encouragingly, all participants checked for a pulse before commencing CPR, reflecting adherence to standard protocols.

Similarly, nearly all ensured that the patient was laid supine on a hard surface before initiating resuscitation, which aligns with established guidelines for effective chest compressions. However, some gaps emerged in the application of CPR techniques. A considerable proportion of respondents acknowledged using different procedures for children and adults, which reflects awareness of variations in resuscitation needs, although a minority applied the same technique irrespective of age.

The table also highlights specific practices related to chest compressions and ventilation. Most respondents adhered to the recommended compression rate of about 100 per minute and correctly followed the 30:2 compression-to-ventilation ratio, which aligns with international CPR guidelines. Nonetheless, a small proportion applied incorrect compression rates or were unsure, indicating the need for periodic retraining to maintain accuracy. Regarding the site and depth of compressions, the majority identified the lower chest and practised the recommended 5–6 cm depth, showing good knowledge of effective technique. However, some respondents opted for shallow compressions or aimed for excessive depth, which could compromise the effectiveness of CPR. Overall, the findings reveal that while the respondents demonstrated strong foundational skills and adherence to best practices in CPR, inconsistencies in technique and knowledge highlight the importance of regular refresher training and practical drills to ensure sustained competence.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀: There is no significant relationship between knowledge of cardiopulmonary resuscitation and practice of cardiopulmonary resuscitation

Table 4: Pearson chi square analysis between knowledge of cardiopulmonary resuscitation and practice of cardiopulmonary resuscitation

Variable		Practice of Cardiopulmonary resuscitation			χ^2	Df	p
		Good Practice	Fair Practice	Poor Practice			
Knowledge of Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation	Good Knowledge	70 (64.2%)	39(35.8%)	0(0)	8.159	4	0.086
	Fair Knowledge	8 (50.0%)	7 (43.8%)	1 (6.3%)			
	Poor Knowledge	1 (100.0%)	0(0)	0(0)			
	Total	79(62.7%)	46(36.5%)	1(0.8%)			

The chi-square analysis in Table 4 examined the relationship between knowledge of cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) and its practice. Although respondents with good knowledge generally demonstrated good or fair practice, and those with fair knowledge also showed a reasonable level of practice, the association was not statistically significant ($p = 0.086$). This implies that while knowledge of CPR appears to influence the quality of practice to some extent, the relationship is not strong enough to be conclusive. The finding suggests

that factors beyond knowledge, such as hands-on experience, frequency of training, and confidence in emergency situations, may play a crucial role in shaping effective CPR practice.

Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that the majority of respondents demonstrated good knowledge of cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), while only a small proportion had fair or poor knowledge. This suggests that most participants were well-informed about the fundamental concepts and techniques of CPR, which is critical for effective response during cardiac emergencies. The outcome supports the work of Guteta (2022), who examined factors influencing CPR practice among nurses in Mizan Tepi University Teaching Hospital and similarly found that knowledge levels were generally high among healthcare providers. High levels of CPR knowledge among respondents can be attributed to prior training sessions, professional exposure, and the increasing emphasis on life-saving skills in healthcare education and practice (Oluwasanmi et al., 2025). However, the presence of individuals with only fair or poor knowledge highlights the need for continuous refresher courses and regular capacity-building programmes, as retention of CPR knowledge often declines over time if not consistently reinforced through training and practical application (Olofin-Samuel et al., 2024). In terms of practice, this study established that nearly two-thirds of respondents demonstrated good CPR practice, with a significant proportion falling within the fair category and a very small percentage exhibiting poor practice. This indicates that while theoretical knowledge of CPR was high, translating that knowledge into consistent, effective practice varied among respondents. The findings are consistent with Ihunanya and Michael (2020), who explored knowledge, attitudes, and practices of CPR among nurses and found similar patterns of variability between knowledge and practice levels. This gap between knowledge and practice may stem from factors such as limited exposure to real-life cardiac emergencies, inadequate opportunities for simulation-based training, or lack of confidence in high-pressure situations. It underscores the importance of regular hands-on practice, drills, and retraining to bridge the gap and ensure that healthcare providers not only know CPR procedures but can also apply them effectively when needed. By strengthening both knowledge and practice, healthcare professionals can significantly improve patient outcomes in cardiac emergencies.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusively, this study has highlighted that the majority of respondents demonstrated adequate knowledge about cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), and this knowledge was reflected in their reported practices. The findings indicate that most of the participants understood key aspects of CPR, such as checking for pulse, ensuring the patient is positioned correctly, and applying the correct compression-to-ventilation ratio, which are all essential for effective resuscitation. These results suggest that the respondents are well positioned to apply their knowledge in real-life situations and are likely to continue utilising these skills whenever the need arises. However, the study also revealed some inconsistencies in the accuracy of certain practices, such as compression depth and the differentiation of procedures between adults and children, underscoring the importance of reinforcing knowledge with regular practical training. The ability of healthcare providers to maintain and apply CPR skills consistently is vital, as timely and accurate intervention can significantly improve patient survival in cardiac emergencies.

Based on these findings, healthcare facilities should prioritise ongoing CPR education and training for all categories of healthcare providers. Knowledge alone may not always translate

into effective action in high-pressure emergency situations, hence the need for continuous capacity building. Regular refresher courses, simulations, and hands-on training sessions are essential to ensure that providers remain confident and up to date with international CPR guidelines. Such structured training programmes will also help address areas where gaps were identified, such as maintaining correct compression rates and depths, and applying age-specific techniques. In addition, incorporating periodic assessments into workplace practice can help track skill retention and identify individuals who may need additional support. By institutionalising CPR education and making it an integral part of professional development, healthcare facilities can strengthen the readiness of their workforce to respond effectively to cardiac emergencies, ultimately improving patient outcomes and saving lives.

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Cite this article:

Author(s), KADRI Adenike Koseganlola R. , SALAKO, Esther Omobolanle, OTUFALE, Taiwo Adenike, OLAOYE, Elizbeth Bolanle , (2025). "Knowledge and Practice of Cardio-Pulmonary Resuscitation among Health Workers in Catholic Hospital Oluyoro and Jericho Specialist Hospital, Ibadan, Oyo State". **Name of the Journal:** Euro Global Contemporary Studies Journal, (EGCSJ.COM), P, 59-71. **DOI:** <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18024358>, Issue: 6, Vol.: 5, Article: 5, Month: December, Year: 2025. Retrieved from <https://www.egcsj.com/all-issues/>

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